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Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Ruthenium(III) with 3-Chloro-1-nitroso-2-naphthol

B. S. MOHITE and V. M. SHINDE

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University,
Kolhapur-416 004

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ISONITROSO derivatives of acetylacetone¹, benzoylacetone², dibenzoylmethane³ and ethylbenzoylacetate⁴ have been used in this laboratory for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium(III). In the present communication, we propose a new chromogenic agent, 3-chloro-1-nitroso-2-naphthol for spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium. The proposed method has proved to be more selective and specific.

Experimental

A stock solution of ruthenium(III) ($1.95 \times 10^{-3} M$) was prepared by dissolving ruthenium trichloride (Johnson Mathey, London) in dil. hydrochloric acid and standardized by known method⁵. Test solutions of lower concentration were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock.

3-Chloro-1-nitroso-2-naphthol was synthesized by reported method⁶ and its 0.1% (w/v) ethanolic solution was used for the estimation of ruthenium. Diverse ion solutions were prepared from analytical grade salts.

Working procedure: An aliquot (25 ml) of aqueous solution containing 10 to 100 μg ruthenium(III), 1 ml 0.1% reagent solution and acetic acid (4.5M in 25 ml total volume) was heated for 30 min in a boiling water bath. After cooling, the solution was extracted in a separatory funnel for 15 sec with 10 ml MIBK (methyl isobutyl ketone). The organic phase was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and absorbance of the yellow-green complex was measured at 595 nm against the reagent blank. The ruthenium contents were computed from the earlier drawn calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The yellow-green ruthenium complex of 3-chloro-1-nitroso-2-naphthol extracted into MIBK from acetic acid solution (4-5 M) absorbs at 595 nm. The ligand shows negligible absorbance at this wave length. The colour system conforms to Beer's

law over the concentration range of 10 to 100 μg of ruthenium(III) per 10 ml of organic phase. The quantitative extraction of the ruthenium complex occurs from 4.5 to 5 M acetic acid solution. Hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid and nitric acid are unsuitable for the extraction. 1 ml 0.1% ethanolic solution of the ligand and 15 sec shaking period is adequate for complete extraction of the complex. The colour of the complex is stable for more than 4 days. Carbontetrachloride, chloroform, benzene, toluene, xylene, amyl alcohol and MIBK were tested as solvent for the extraction, but MIBK was found to be the only effective solvent. Job's variation method and mole ratio method indicate the formation of 1:3 (metal to reagent) complex. The tolerance limit of the various cations and anions are shown in Table 1. The ions showing strong interference in ruthenium estimation

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS
Ru(III) = 30 μg

Tolerance limit	Ions
mg	
0.1	La(III), Ce(IV).
0.2	Au(III), Pt(IV).
0.3	EDTA, SCN ⁻ .
0.4	Cd(II).
0.5	Th(IV), Zr(IV), Mo(VI), PO ₄ ³⁻ , C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻ , tartrate.
1.0	Co(II), Cr(III), Ir(III).
2.0	Te(IV), citrate, F ⁻ .
3.0	Ni(II), Se(IV), U(VI).
5.0	Zn(II), Mn(II), Hg(II), W(VI), SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ .
Interfering ions	Pd(II), Fe(II), Rh(III), Os(VIII), ascorbate and thiourea.

by the proposed method are Pd, Fe(III), Rh(III), Os(VIII), ascorbate and thiourea. Interference due to iron(III) is removed by its prior extraction with mesityl oxide⁷. Palladium(II) is separated from ruthenium(III) by its extraction into MIBK from cold aqueous solution containing 4.5 M acetic acid and 5 ml 0.1% ligand solution and finally estimated in the organic phase; the aqueous phase is evaporated to dryness and the residue is taken up in water for estimation of ruthenium by the proposed method.

The standard deviation and coefficient of variation of the absorbance was found to be 0.004 and 1.02%, respectively for 50 μg ruthenium.

A comparison of the proposed method with some of the earlier tried ligands (Table 2) showed

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

Ligand	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$	Molar absorptivity 1 mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Colour stability hr
Isonitrosoacetylacetone	0.022	4.5×10^4	36
Isonitrosobenzoylacetone	0.018	5.4×10^4	6
Isonitrosodibenzoylmethane	0.024	4.1×10^4	48
Isonitrosoethylbenzoylacetate	0.041	2.4×10^4	24
3-Chloro-1-nitroso-2-naphthol	0.011	8.6×10^4	>96

TABLE 3—ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Composition of mixture and amount taken μg	Percentage recovery of ruthenium
Ru, 50 ; Au, 200 ; Pt, 200	99.7
Ru, 50 ; U, 3000 ; Se, 3000 ; Ni, 3000	99.5
Ru, 50 ; Co, 1000 ; Ir, 1000 ; Mn, 1000	99.7
Ru, 50 ; Fe, 5000*	99.7
Ru, 50 ; Pd, 500*	99.5

*Iron is removed by prior extraction with mesityl oxide⁷ and palladium is eliminated as described in the text.

that the proposed ligand has high molar absorptivity, better sensitivity and more stability. The method is also suitable for the determination of

ruthenium in synthetic mixtures containing Au(III), Pt(IV), U(VI), Se(IV), Ni(II), Mn(II), Co(II) and Ir(III) (Table 3).

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